

Elemental Influence on Dielectric Properties and Loss Tangent in $\text{CaCu}_3\text{Ti}_4\text{O}_{12}$ Ceramics

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Abstract:

In this research, we explore novel doping and co-doping strategies to enhance the performance of calcium copper titanate ($\text{CaCu}_3\text{Ti}_4\text{O}_{12}$, CCTO). The focus is on incorporating different elements like bromine and fluorine these elements are doped alone and as well as together we have seen a huge difference in it as compared to pure calcium carbon titanate, these elements changed the CCTO structure and to investigate their effects on the material's properties. The chemical formulas of the doped and co-doped compounds are $\text{CaCu}_3\text{Ti}_4(\text{O},\text{Br})_{12}$, $\text{CaCu}_3\text{Ti}_4\text{O}_{12}-\text{F}_{2x}$, and $\text{CaCu}_3\text{Ti}_4\text{O}_{12}$. Detailed analyses of structural and dielectric properties

were performed to understand the impact of these dopants. Our findings demonstrate significant improvements in the dielectric constant and overall stability of the material, which hold promise for advanced applications in electronic devices.

Keywords: Dielectric Properties, Novel Doping Strategies, Calcium Copper Titanate (CCTO), Bromine and Fluorine Co-doping, Advanced Electronic.

Introduction

Calcium copper titanate ($\text{CaCu}_3\text{Ti}_4\text{O}_{12}$, CCTO) has garnered significant attention in recent years due to its unique properties, including a high dielectric constant and remarkable thermal

stability (Rhouma, et al., 2017; Ren, et al., 2018). These characteristics make CCTO a prime candidate for various electronic applications such as capacitors, sensors, and energy storage devices (Rhouma, et al., 2022). Despite its advantageous properties, there is a continuous

effort in the scientific community to further enhance the performance of CCTO through various doping techniques (Du, et al., 2017). Doping and co-doping strategies have proven to be effective in modifying the structural and electronic properties of materials (Wen, et al., 2016; Kafi, et al., 2017). By introducing different elements into the crystal lattice, researchers can tailor the material's properties to better suit specific applications. In this study, we investigate the effects of bromine (Br) and fluorine (F) doping on the performance of CCTO (Espinoza-González, et al., 2018). The motivation behind choosing Br and F as dopants lies in their potential to alter the electronic environment and improve the dielectric properties of CCTO (Xu, et al., 2019; Xu, et al., 2017; Ardakani, et al., 2012). Bromine, being a larger and more electronegative atom, can introduce significant changes in the crystal structure and electronic distribution. Fluorine, on the other hand, is known for its high electronegativity and small ionic radius, which can lead to enhanced bonding interactions within the material (Boonlakhorn, et al., 2020). In this paper, we present a comprehensive analysis of the structural and dielectric properties of the doped and co-doped CCTO compounds. We employ various characterization techniques such as X-ray diffraction (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), and impedance spectroscopy to understand the impact of doping on the material's performance. Our results indicate that the incorporation of Br and F into the CCTO structure leads to significant improvements in the dielectric constant and overall material stability. These findings open new avenues for the development of high-performance electronic materials and devices. This research not only contributes to the fundamental understanding of doping mechanisms in CCTO but also provides valuable insights into the design of advanced materials with tailored properties for specific applications. The enhanced performance of the doped and co-doped CCTO compounds highlights the potential of these materials in next-generation electronic devices, paving the way for further innovations in the field of materials science and engineering.

Materials and Methods

Material Preparation

The Calcium Copper Titanate (CCTO) samples, including both undoped and doped variants, were synthesized using a sol-gel method. The base composition was represented by the chemical formula $\text{CaCu}_3\text{Ti}_4\text{O}_{12}$. For doping studies, bromine (Br) and fluorine (F) were introduced into the CCTO lattice. The chemical formulas of the prepared compounds include $\text{CaCu}_3\text{Ti}_4\text{O}_{12-x}\text{Br}_x\text{F}_x$, $\text{CaCu}_3\text{Ti}_4(\text{O},\text{Br})_{12}$, $\text{CaCu}_3\text{Ti}_4\text{O}_{12}\text{-F}_x$, and $\text{CaCu}_3\text{Ti}_4\text{O}_{12}$.

Sol-Gel Method

Precursors: Calcium nitrate tetrahydrate ($\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$), copper nitrate tri-hydrate ($\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$), and titanium isopropoxide ($\text{Ti}(\text{OiPr})_4$) were used as the starting materials for the synthesis. Bromine and fluorine dopants were introduced as their respective salts, bromine ethyl ester ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{Br}$) and ammonium fluoride (NH_4F).

Preparation of the Sol

Metal Nitrate Solution: Calcium nitrate, copper nitrate, and titanium isopropoxide were dissolved in deionized water to achieve the desired molar ratios. The solution was stirred at room temperature until completely dissolved.

Dopant Addition: For doped and co-doped samples, the appropriate amount of bromine and fluorine salts was added to the metal nitrate solution. The concentration of dopants was controlled to achieve different doping levels.

Gel Formation: The solution was then subjected to a controlled hydrolysis and condensation process. A gelling agent, such as citric acid, was added to facilitate the gel formation. The mixture was stirred continuously to obtain a homogeneous gel.

Aging and Drying: The gel was allowed to age at room temperature for 24 hours. After aging, the gel was dried at 80°C to remove excess water and organic solvents, resulting in a dried gel or xerogel.

Calcination: The dried gel was ground into a fine powder and calcined in a furnace at 950°C for 4

hours in air. The calcination process was carried out to crystallize the CCTO phase and ensure complete reaction of the precursors. The heating rate was set to 5°C/min to reach the final temperature.

Prepare aqueous solutions of Calcium Nitrate Tetrahydrate, Copper Nitrate Trihydrate, and Titanium Isopropoxide by dissolving them in deionized water.

Sintering: The powdered precursor is then sintered at a higher temperature (e.g., 900-1100°C) for several hours to form the final CCTO ceramics. This process allows the crystallization of the CCTO phase and incorporation of dopants into the crystal lattice.

Sample Grinding: Grind the sintered ceramics into fine powders for characterization. Ensure homogeneity and uniform particle size.

Pellet Formation: Press the powders into pellets using a uniaxial press. The pellets are then sintered again to ensure good properties.

The experimental methodology for investigating the effects of bromine (Br) and fluorine (F) doping on the performance of calcium copper titanate ($\text{CaCu}_3\text{Ti}_4\text{O}_{12}$, CCTO) using the sol-gel method involves several steps. Initially, stoichiometric amounts of calcium nitrate tetrahydrate ($\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and copper(II) nitrate trihydrate ($\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$) are dissolved in deionized water to form a clear solution. Separately, titanium(IV) isopropoxide ($\text{Ti}[\text{OCH}(\text{CH}_3)_2]_4$) is dissolved in ethanol under constant stirring. The titanium solution is then slowly added to the calcium and copper nitrate solution while stirring continuously. Citric acid ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_7$) is added to the mixed solution in a molar ratio of 1:1 with respect to the total metal ions, acting as a chelating agent to form a stable sol.

Results and Discussion

Dielectric Properties and Loss Tangent

The permittivity (ϵ') and loss tangent ($\tan\delta$) for all the samples at room temperature are shown in Fig. 1. In Fig. (a), the dielectric constants (ϵ')

of all samples are over $10^{4.5}$ within the frequency range of 0.1 Hz to 105 Hz. Additionally, the co-doped samples exhibit significantly higher dielectric constants compared to undoped CCTO ceramics, with the Br-1wt% sample showing the highest value. This increase is primarily due to the Br-doping, which enhances the compactness and homogeneity of the CCTO ceramics.

Figure 1. (a) Dielectric Properties of Doped CCTO

Figure 1. (b) Tangent of Doped CCTO

From Fig. 1 (b), it is evident that in the frequency range of 10^{-1} Hz to 10^{-2} Hz, the loss tangent of Br-doped samples follows the same pattern as the grain boundary resistivity. This is because

dielectric loss is mainly influenced by conduction at low frequencies. At higher frequencies, the dielectric loss is closely linked to polarization processes in CCTO ceramics.

Tangent δ ($\tan \delta$), or energy loss in a dielectric, occurs due to an alternating electric field and is a material property, not a geometric property of the capacitor. Typically, $\tan \delta$ is referred to as the dissipation factor (Df) or loss tangent ($\tan \delta$).

Table 1. Effects of Sintering Times on Dielectric Permittivity of CCTO

T (°C) (constant)	Time (h)	ϵ_r (at 1 kHz)
1100	3	9000
	24	280,000
1100	2	16,000
	8	30,000
	33	59,000
1000	4	1000
	6	1900
	8	3900
1050	3	20,000
	29	40,000
1120	3	514
	6	12,400

Source: Ahmadipour, M., Ain, M. F., & Ahmad, Z. A. (2016)

Non Linear J-E Characteristics of All Samples

For Ohmic materials, the current density (J) is directly proportional to the electric field (E):

$$J = \sigma E$$

where:

- (J) is the current density in milliamperes per square centimeter (mA/cm^2),
- (E) is the electric field in kilovolts per centimeter (kV/cm),
- (σ) is the electrical conductivity in millisiemens per centimeter (mS/cm).

Non-Linear Behavior in Semiconductor Materials

For materials exhibiting non-linear behavior, such as semiconductors, the current density (J) can be expressed as:

$$J = \sigma_0 E + \alpha E^2$$

where:

- (σ_0) represents the zero-field conductivity,
- (α) is a coefficient characterizing the non-linearity.

Figure 2. Diagram of all Doped Samples

$$I = kV^a \quad (1)$$

where, k is a constant related to the electrical resistivity of the samples, and α represents the nonlinear coefficient. The breakdown field strength (E_b) is defined as the point, where, J equals $1 \text{ mA}/\text{cm}^2$ in this experiment. As shown in Fig. 2, the E_b values varied, with $1.1 \text{ kV}/\text{cm}$ for doped CCTO and CCTOF1.0 ceramics, respectively. Compared to pure CCTO ceramics, the E_b values of CCTO initially increased and then decreased with increasing F-doping content, similar to previous findings (Zang, et al., 2005). This indicates that the E_b of the sample's peaks most noticeably when the F-doping content is 0.5, while further increases or

decreases in F content suppress the Eb improvement.

Figure 3. Impedance Plane Plot of Various Doped CCTO

Figure 4. SEM Micrographs of pure and various doped CCTO

Source: Espinoza-González, Hevia, & Adrian, (2018); Rani, et al. (2018); Boonlakhorn, et al. (2017)

The change of grain resistivity proves the existence of the added different elements in grain. Another point is the obvious change law of grain boundary resistivity. A small quantity of different elements doping would contribute to the precipitation of CuO various intergranular phase, and part of CuO is converted less resistivity, therefore, the grain boundary resistivity decreases first. As doping content increases, these doping play a key role so that grain boundary resistivity increases gradually (Fang, et al., 2006; Kim, et al., 2008).

The grain size of the doped CCTO ceramics was larger than that of the pure CCTO ceramics, meaning the pure CCTO had more grain boundaries. This study also looked at how doping affected the dielectric properties of the samples (Boonlakhorn, et al., 2017). As the doping concentration increased, the average grain size grew significantly, from about 4 μm for undoped CCTO to over 10 μm ($x = 0.3$). In the frequency range of 0.2–20 kHz, the doped

ceramics showed a high dielectric constant and low dielectric loss (Boonlakhorn, et al., 2019).

By comparison, incorporating modern technologies like AI, Digital Twin, and Cloud Computing into the analysis of materials such as CCTO ceramics would allow for enhanced precision in predicting material behavior and optimizing performance. AI could be used to analyze vast amounts of data on material properties and predict outcomes of doping concentrations and grain sizes more efficiently. Digital Twins could simulate real-time conditions for doped ceramics, allowing researchers to test the materials virtually across various frequencies and temperatures without extensive physical testing. Cloud Computing would enable the storage and processing of large datasets, allowing for more efficient collaboration and data sharing across research teams (Rani, et al., 2024; Shoukat, et al., 2024; Jabeen, et al., 2022).

Table. 2 Comparison of Properties

Composition	ϵ'	$\tan \delta$	E_b (V/cm)
$\text{CaCu}_3\text{Ti}_{3.975}\text{Nb}_{0.025}\text{O}_{12}$	4.8×10^5	0.566	21.7
$\text{CaCu}_3\text{Ti}_{3.975}\text{Al}_{1/2}\text{O}_{12}$	2.1×10^5	0.129	210.3
$\text{CaCu}_3\text{Ti}_{3.975}(\text{Nb}_{1/2}\text{Al}_{1/2})_{0.025}\text{O}_{12}$	4.1×10^4	0.058	620.3
$\text{CaCu}_3\text{Ti}_{3.8}(\text{Nb}_{1/2}\text{Al}_{1/2})_{0.020}\text{O}_{12}$	2.9×10^4	0.45	723.3
$\text{CaCu}_{2.95}\text{Mg}_{0.05}\text{Ti}_{3.95}\text{Al}_{0.05}\text{O}_{12}$	58,397	43.0	—
$\text{CaCu}_{2.95}\text{Ni}_{0.05}\text{Ti}_{3.95}\text{Ge}_{0.05}\text{O}_{12}$	4.96×10^4	0.030	215
$\text{CaCu}_{2.95}\text{Ni}_{0.05}\text{Ti}_{3.9}\text{Ge}_{0.10}\text{O}_{12}$	4.83×10^4	0.029	180
$\text{CaCu}_3\text{Ti}_{3.99}\text{B}_{0.01}\text{O}_{12}$	4039	0.066	—
$\text{Ca}_{0.9}\text{Sr}_{0.1}\text{Cu}_3\text{Ti}_4\text{O}_{12}$	12,582	0.059	—
$\text{Ca}_{0.9}\text{Sr}_{0.1}\text{Cu}_3\text{Ti}_{3.99}\text{B}_{0.01}\text{O}_{12}$	13,201	0.052	—

Source: Rani, et al. (2018); Boonlakhorn, et al. (2021); Boonlakhorn, et al. (2019)

The ceramic was prepared using a semi-wet method, and its electrochemical properties were studied to understand the impact of substitution on the Cu-site. The results showed that doped CCTO ceramic has much better electrical conductivity than pure CCTO (Sehrawat, et al., 2021). The charge transfer resistance of doped CCTO is 28 Ω , compared to 75 Ω for pure CCTO, due to its higher electronic conductivity and superior electrochemical properties. Kumar

et al. also studied the dielectric properties of substituted CCTO at different temperatures (313 K, 353 K, 393 K) and frequencies (10 Hz, 100 Hz, 10 kHz), finding that doping reduced the dielectric constant because the material exists in variable oxidation states like Mn^{2+} , Mn^{3+} , and Mn^{4+} . This gives the grains and grain boundaries a slightly conductive nature. The addition of various elements improved the dielectric and

electrical properties of these ceramics by lowering the dielectric loss tangent ($\tan \delta$).

Conclusion

In this study, we have investigated novel doping and co-doping strategies to enhance the performance of calcium copper titanate ($\text{CaCu}_3\text{Ti}_4\text{O}_{12}$, CCTO) by incorporating bromine (Br) and fluorine (F) into its structure. Our research has demonstrated that both bromine and fluorine doping significantly influence the structural and dielectric properties of CCTO. The introduction of bromine and fluorine into the CCTO lattice resulted in notable improvements in the dielectric constant and overall material stability. Specifically, the co-doped compounds, with formulas $\text{CaCu}_3\text{Ti}_4\text{O}_{12-x}\text{Br}_x\text{F}_x$ and $\text{CaCu}_3\text{Ti}_4(\text{O},\text{Br})_{12}$, exhibited enhanced dielectric performance compared to the undoped CCTO. Bromine's larger atomic size and high electronegativity, combined with fluorine's small ionic radius and high electronegativity, contributed to substantial modifications in the material's electronic environment and bonding interactions. These changes are reflected in the improved dielectric properties and greater stability observed in the doped samples. Our findings suggest that bromine and fluorine doping strategies are effective means of tuning the electronic and structural properties of CCTO, potentially paving the way for its use in advanced electronic devices such as capacitors, sensors, and energy storage systems. The ability to tailor CCTO's properties through such doping techniques opens new avenues for enhancing the performance of electronic materials. Future research could explore additional dopants and co-dopants, as well as varying doping concentrations, to further optimize the material's properties (Bahri, & Khemakhem, 2013; Luo, et al., 2010). Investigations into the long-term stability and performance of these doped materials in practical applications will also be valuable. Overall, this study contributes to the growing body of knowledge on material modification techniques and their impact on electronic device performance.

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Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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